

APPROACH FOR IDENTIFYING SCIENTIFIC AND OPERATIONALLY SIGNIFICANT REGIONS FOR ESA'S PROSPECT INSTRUMENT ON THE MOON. C. Orgel¹, S. Boazman¹, M. Schwinning², T. Warren³, T. Junkermann², M. Hutton², D. Heather¹, and the PROSPECT Landing Site Working Group*. ¹ESTEC, European Space Agency, Keplerlaan 1, Noordwijk 2201AZ, Netherlands (csilla.orgel@ext.esa.int), ²ESOC, European Space Operations Centre, Robert-Bosch-Straße 5, 64293 Darmstadt, Germany, ³University of Oxford, Oxford OX1 2JD, United Kingdom

Introduction: The Package for Resource Observation and in-Situ Prospecting for Exploration, Commercial Characterisation and Testing (PROSPECT) is a payload in development by ESA which will perform an assessment of the volatile inventory in the lunar regolith (down to ~1 m), and complete elemental and isotopic analyses to determine the abundance and origin of any volatiles discovered [1, 2].

Intermittently sunlit areas near the lunar South Pole are estimated to harbour thermal conditions permitting long term stability of water ice and other volatiles [e.g., 3, 4]. Leading thermophysical model results [5, 6] indicate to have temperatures that permit the stability of water ice at about 30% of the lunar south polar terrain poleward of 80°S (Figure 1) and zones of thermal stability are preferentially distributed in the top few 10s of cm [7].

Figure 1: Left: Areas in which volatile stability is predicted both by data from [5] and [6] at 120 m/pix spatial resolution. Note that intersection is only possible in areas of mutual coverage (South Pole to 80°S), within the bounding box of data from [5]. Map from [7]. Right: Histogram of depth to water ice thermal stability from [5] and [6].

This abstract aims to present the approach of searching for candidate landing sites where both science (e.g., presence of water ice) and operational requirements (e.g., solar illumination, Earth visibility, slopes) are satisfied for PROSPECT and showcases a process from analysing dataset at coarse resolution of 120 m/pix down to high resolution of 1 m/pix.

Selection Process Step 1: We applied a pixel-by-pixel analysis and prepared Boolean rasters by combining datasets (e.g., Lunar Orbiter Laser Altimeter (LOLA) Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) [8], slope maps, average illumination and Earth visibility maps [9] and water ice stability models [5, 6]) sampled at a

coarse spatial resolution of 120 m/pix extending the South Pole to 80°S at the cardinal meridians similarly to [7]. Figure 2 shows the result of 49 Points of Interest (POIs) overlaid on LOLA DEM where scientific (water ice is present) and engineering constraints (slopes of <10°, illumination of 30% or more, and Earth visibility of average 50% or more) were both satisfied. POIs with the size of at least ~500 m (4 contiguous pixels) diameter were taken further into consideration and down-selected to 18 POIs based on a science traceability matrix and scoring system [10]. Then, the top 4 highest ranked POIs were analysed further with mixed resolution datasets adding Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter Camera (LROC) Narrow Angle Camera (NAC) Shape from Shading (SfS) DEMs (5 m/pix) [11], and illumination models (5–20 m/pix) [12] to the 120 m/pix resolution datasets. Important to note that the analysis was carried out with the highest resolution datasets available within the time frame of the analysis.

Figure 2: LOLA elevation map (30 m/pixel) is overlaid with all 49 POIs and the final 18 POIs after applying a science traceability matrix and scoring system. Map from [10].

Caveats: The caveat of both [7] and [10] studies are that they use (i) average solar illumination and Earth visibility on the lunar surface [9] instead of data representative for a dedicated mission timeframe, and (ii) various spatial resolution datasets from 120 to 5 m/pix.

Selection Process Step 2: A more detailed and sophisticated pixel-by-pixel approach has been developed to identify potential ROIs for PROSPECT. Similarly to the first step, the process checks for

feasibility of each pixel in a pre-defined region fulfilling all requirements listed below at 1 m/pix spatial resolution.

- There are at least 3 mission windows of 10 days or more available within the year from Oct 2027 - Oct 2028. Mission windows are continuous periods of (i) illumination at assumed solar panel height and (ii) Earth visibility at assumed antenna height.
- Slopes are less than 10 degrees, measured at the scale of the lander footprint (horizontal distance between opposing legs on the surface).
- Thermal conditions indicate feasible conditions for water ice stability between 0 and 1 metre depths (Figure 3).

Figure 3: O3DTM thermal model [6] derived at 1 m/pix spatial resolution overlaid on hillshade within a test area of 1500 m x 1500 m box indicated to be suitable in the step 1 selection process. Red indicates that water ice is not stable, while blue shows that water ice could be stable.

- All pixels around the investigated pixel in a radius equal to the assumed landing accuracy satisfy the above criteria at the same time (Figure 4).

Next Steps:

- The development of a process to quantify the confidence level of the generated DEM and its associated data products.
- Apply newly developed software to compute illumination conditions quicker [13].
- Perform hazard assessment at candidate sites: craters $D > 50$ m and boulders $D > 2$ m.

- Compile lessons learned.
- Searching for additional candidate sites covering the period of Oct 2027 - Oct 2028 within various locations in the south polar region
- Searching for additional candidate sites covering the period from Oct 2028 – Oct 2029.

Figure 4: Region of Interest satisfying the scientific and operational requirements within a test area of 1500 m x 1500 m box. Note that 50 m radius around each pixel satisfy the listed criteria.

Key message: Results show that the introduction of time-dependent high-resolution data significantly reduced the feasible areas compared to the area deemed feasible by coarse resolution and average visibility data.

References: [1] Trautner, R. et al., (2024) *Front. Space Technol.*, Sec. Space Exploration, Vol. 5. [2] Heather, D. et al., (2025) in *ELS*, Abst. #XXXX, [3] Ingersoll, A. P.T. et al., (1992). *Icarus* 100, 40–47. [4] Hayne, P.O. et al. (2020). *Nature Astronomy* 5, 169–175. [5] Paige, D. A. et al., (2010). *Science* 330(6003): 479. [6] Warren, T. et al., (2020). <https://github.com/tw7044/O3DTM/>. [7] Orgel et al. (2022), *53rd Lunar Planet. Sci. Conf.*, Abstract# 2434. [8] Smith, D.E., et al., (2017). *Icarus* 283, 70 – 91. [9] Mazarico, E. et al., (2011). *Icarus* 211(2): 1066–81. [10] Boazman et al. (2024). *Icarus*, 421, 116240. [11] Mazarico et al. (2023) LROC NAC Sfs DEM dataset at 5 m/pix. [12] Schwinning, M., (2021). Mission Analysis for Future Lunar Surface Exploration. Dissertation Universität Stuttgart. [13] Junkermann, T. et al., (2025) in *ELS*, Abst. #XXXX.